

Electrochemical Study of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} Complexes with Dithiodipropionic Acid

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The interaction of metal ion (Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+}) with dithiodipropionic acid has been investigated by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques. Two chelates having 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 mono-ratios of metal to ligand are formed simultaneously over the pH range 3.3-5.3. Their stability constants have been determined by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method and refined by alternative methods viz., least square treatment, correction term and convergence formulae. The values of overall ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the complexation reactions are also evaluated at 30°.

SAXENA and coworkers¹⁻³ have carried out extensive studies on the complexation of thiols with several metals. This communication reports the formation and composition of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} complexes with dithiodipropionic acid employing pH-metric and conductometric titration technique, determination of their stability constants at 20, 30 and 40° by Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method, least square treatment, correction term and convergence formulae.

The overall changes in thermodynamic functions, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS , accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined at 30°. There is no reference in the literature on the present investigations.

Experimental

Dithiodipropionic acid [$\text{S}_2(\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOH})_2$], (referred as RSSR) of 99% purity was obtained from Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York. Copper sulphate, nickel sulphate, cobalt chloride and manganese chloride used were of B. D. H. AnalaR grade. Metal contents of their solutions were estimated by standard methods. Freshly prepared solutions of dithiodipropionic acid (DTDPA) were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation.

Measurements of pH were made on a Toshniwal digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) with glass calomel electrode assembly in a nitrogen atmosphere and thermostated titration cell. Conductance measurements were carried out with an electronic eye type conductometer. The experimental procedure was the same as described earlier¹⁻³ and involved a series of pH-metric and conductometric titration of DTDPA with 0.1 M NaOH in the absence and presence of metal ion at various ligand to metal ratios.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction between M^{2+} (Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+}) and dithiodipropionic acid was determined by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali (Fig. 1).

The appearance of only one inflection (Fig. 1; curve 1) after two mole of base per mole of ligand (DTDPA) corresponds to the neutralisation of two

Fig. 1. pH titration of the solutions.

- Curve (1) 4×10^{-3} M DTDPA
(2) 4×10^{-3} M DTDPA + 1.33×10^{-3} M Cu^{2+}
(3) 4×10^{-3} M DTDPA + 2×10^{-3} M Cu^{2+}
(4) 4×10^{-3} M DTDPA + 4×10^{-3} M Cu^{2+}

carboxyl hydrogens in a single step. Hence, if free dithiodipropionic acid having two replaceable

TABLE 1—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ AND Mn²⁺ COMPLEXES AT 20, 30 AND 40°

Method	log K _{stab}	20°				30°				40°			
		Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mn ²⁺
[A]	log K ₁	3.72	3.58	3.34	3.04	4.00	3.85	3.58	3.24	4.33	4.17	3.88	3.49
	log K ₂	3.34	3.24	2.99	2.86	3.57	3.45	3.16	3.00	3.85	3.72	3.38	3.19
	log β	7.06	6.82	6.33	5.90	7.57	7.30	6.74	6.24	8.18	7.89	7.26	6.68
[B]	log K ₁	3.65	3.59	3.31	3.05	3.92	3.86	3.55	3.25	4.25	4.19	3.85	3.50
	log K ₂	3.27	3.25	2.96	2.86	3.49	3.46	3.13	3.00	3.77	3.73	3.35	3.20
	log β	6.92	6.84	6.27	5.91	7.41	7.32	6.68	6.25	8.02	7.92	7.30	6.70
Uncertainty		(±0.02)	(±0.03)	(±0.03)	(±0.02)	(±0.02)	(±0.03)	(±0.03)	(±0.04)	(±0.04)	(±0.03)	(±0.03)	(±0.02)

[A] and [B] represent Bjerrum's and least square methods, respectively. The values of stability constants were also obtained by convergence formulae and correction term method and found to be in close proximity of A and B values but the same have not been recorded for the sake of brevity.

hydrogen ions is denoted as H₂A

the reaction between 'm' interval of 0-2 may be represented in a single step by the equation

The absence of an inflection at 1 mole of NaOH indicates that the acidities of both the hydrogens are fairly comparable in magnitude and that the two ligands species H₂A and HA⁻ exist in equilibrium in the pH ranges corresponding to the value of 0-2 mole of NaOH.

Addition of an equimolar amount of Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ or Mn²⁺ ions (Fig. 1 ; curve 4) alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of chelate formation. It is seen that the reaction of the ligand and the metal ion results in the lowering of buffer region and the displacement of hydrogen (at different pH for different metal ions) to form 1:1 chelate which may be expressed by the equation

On further addition of NaOH, an inflection at ≈3 mole of NaOH, per mole of ligand is observed, which may be attributed to the disproportionation of the 1:1 chelate to the more stable 1:2 chelate and corresponding hydroxides in accordance with the equation

Addition of NaOH beyond 3 mole of NaOH per mole of ligand causes another inflection at ≈4 mole of NaOH per mole of ligand due to the decomposition of the 1:2 chelate to disodium salt of acid and metal hydroxide in accordance with the equation

When two mole of ligand are added to M²⁺ (Fig. 1 ; curve 3) the curve shows the inflections at

2 and 3 mole of NaOH per mole of ligand corresponding to the formation of 1:2 chelate and its decomposition into disodium salt of acid and hydroxide in accordance with the equation

This is further confirmed by the inflections at ≈2 and 2.66 mole of NaOH per mole of ligand (Fig. 1 ; curve 2) when the ratio of metal to ligand has decreased to 1:3.

Conductometric titrations :

Conductometric titrations of the solutions containing metal ions and the ligand mixed in different ratios were also performed against 0.1 M NaOH and the breaks in titration curves revealed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal to ligand complexes as obtained from the pH titration curves.

Stability constants :

Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum's⁵ method has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes from potentiometric titration data and the values were further refined by using (i) least square treatment⁶, (ii) correction term⁶ and (iii) convergence formulas⁷ as recorded in Table 1. The values of log K₁ and log K₂ at 20, 30 and 40° were read directly from the formation curves at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\bar{n}=1.5$ (not given for the sake of brevity) and recorded in Table 1. The stability has the order Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Mn²⁺. The log K_{stab} values increase with rise in temperature indicating that the complexes become more stable with rise in temperature.

Thermodynamic functions :

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined at 30° with the help of standard equations⁸. The results are given in Table 2.

The negative values of ΔG show that the driving tendency of the complexation reaction is from left to right and the reaction tends to proceed spontaneously. The values of enthalpy changes are nega-

TABLE 2—OVERALL CHANGES IN THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS

Metal complex	ΔG k cal/mole	ΔH k cal/mole	ΔS cals/deg./mole
Cu ²⁺	-10.37 (± 0.08)	-25.59 (± 0.30)	-50.23 (± 0.40)
Ni ²⁺	-10.12 (± 0.06)	-22.85 (± 0.27)	-42.01 (± 0.35)
Co ²⁺	-9.29 (± 0.05)	-17.82 (± 0.25)	-26.86 (± 0.35)
Mn ²⁺	-8.64 (± 0.07)	-14.62 (± 0.20)	-19.73 (± 0.28)

tive indicating the exothermic nature of the reaction and the changes in entropy (negative) are related to the decrease in the number of particles on complex formation.

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